

corresponding values of α . It is well known^{1,2} that the presence of surfactants affects the kinetics of electrode processes and consequently αn_a (and hence α) values are also affected. Recently, Singh et al^{1,2} while studying the suppression of Ni(II) maxima have compared the efficacies of the suppressors in terms of αn_a values at the concentrations where maximum is just suppressed. The order of αn_a values (which should also be the order of α -values) at any comparative situation for different surfactants should signify the extent to which the addition of ionic and non-ionic surfactants pushes the electrode reaction of nitrobenzene towards irreversibility. In the present study this push towards irreversibility at the point of just suppression is in the following order :

Cationic : LPC > CPC > CDBAC

Anionic : DSSS > SLS > DBS

Non-ionic : Gelatin > 2-ethoxy ethanol > ethyldigol > Triton X-100. Thus CDBAC, DBS and Triton X-100 eliminate the polarographic maximum with least influence on the kinetics of electron transfer.

The effect of increasing concentration of the surfactants beyond the stage of just suppression on αn_a values has also been investigated and it has been observed that a decrease in the values of αn_a takes place. From this it is inferred^{1,5-1,7} that the electrode reaction of nitrobenzene becomes more irreversible at higher concentrations of the surfactants.

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A Note on General Mathematical Expression for Stress-Strain Behaviour and Molecular Structure

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FROM statistical considerations, by a rigorous but straightforward mathematical treatment we obtained the following expression for the energy stored, $\Delta W^{(def)}$, due to deformation of a rubber-elastic polymer network at constant temperature T ,

$$\Delta W^{(def)} = nkT[(3/2)(L/nl)^2(\alpha_x^2 + \alpha_y^2 + \alpha_z^2 - 3) + (9/20)(L/nl)^4(\alpha_x^4 + \alpha_y^4 + \alpha_z^4 - 3) + (99/350)(L/nl)^6(\alpha_x^6 + \alpha_y^6 + \alpha_z^6 - 3) + \dots] - KT \ln \alpha_x \alpha_y \alpha_z = \dots \quad (1)$$

For the last term of above equation, i.e., $KT \ln \alpha_x \alpha_y \alpha_z$ at present we assumed Flory's approach¹.

Where

n = number of effective flexible links in the polymer chain between adjacent crosslinks.

l = length of each flexible link.

k = Boltzmann constant.

T = absolute temperature.

L = average length per chain, in each of x , y and z directions.

and α_x , α_y and α_z are factors by which L is deformed in x , y and z directions. That is in x direction L changes to $L \alpha_x$ in y direction to $L \alpha_y$ and in z direction to $L \alpha_z$.

For elongation of a sample by a factor of L at constant volume^{6,7} the tensile force, τ , per initial cross-sectional unit area as :

$$\tau = \frac{kT}{L^2 l} \left[\alpha^{-1} \left(\frac{L\alpha}{nl} \right) - \alpha^{-\frac{3}{2}} \alpha^{-1} \left(\frac{L\alpha^{-\frac{1}{2}}}{nl} \right) \right] \dots \quad (2)$$

$$\text{or } \tau = (kT/L^2 l) [3(L/nl)(\alpha - 1/\alpha^3)$$

$$+ (9/5)(L/nl)^3 \left(\alpha^3 - \frac{1}{\alpha^3} \right)$$

$$+ (297/175)(L/nl)^5 \left(\alpha^5 - \frac{1}{\alpha^5} \right) + \dots] \dots \quad (3)$$

where α^{-1} denotes inverse Langevin function.

It is obvious that the first term of the right-hand

Fig. 1

side of above equation corresponds to Flory's equation and the first two terms together is similar to empirical equation of Mooney. But in our equation, unlike Mooneys, there is no unknown parameter. The curves from first (Curve C) approximation (Flory's) and from the second approximation (Curve B which is similar to Mooney's) have been compared with the curves from a typical experimental result^{9,10} and the curve 'A' from our general equation (3). The theoretical curves are for $n=50$ and $T=300^\circ\text{K}$. The experimental curve is for $n=40$ and $T=300^\circ\text{K}$, approximately.

The theoretical results from Flory and others^{3,4} (which came out as first approximation) and existing experimental results seem to support the new statistical approach to the theory of rubber elasticity.

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Colorimetric Determination of Organotrithiocarbonates and Mercaptans (via Trithiocarbonate Formation)

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ORGANOTRITHIOCARBONATES may be considered as salts of the corresponding trithiocarbonic acids(I) and are characterised

by the presence of $-\text{C}-\text{S}^-$ group. In spite of the numerous valuable applications of organotrithiocarbonates in industry, medicine and agriculture, their estimation did not attract much attention. Verma and coworkers¹⁻⁶ have very recently developed various aqueous and non-aqueous redox methods for the determination of organotrithiocarbonates. In aqueous medium the methods were also extended to the determination of mercaptans after their quantitative transformation (with carbon disulphide and alkali) into organotrithiocarbonates.

Organotrithiocarbonates react with nickel(II) in slightly acidic medium to form brown coloured precipitates, which can be brought into solutions in the presence of acetone. The absorbance of the yellowish-brown coloured solution thus obtained can be measured photometrically. These observations have been exploited to develop a colorimetric method for the determination of small quantities of organotrithiocarbonates. The method has also been extended to the determination of mercaptans after their quantitative transformation into organotrithiocarbonates. The proposed methods are simple, accurate and reliable. The procedure is less time-consuming and may be used for routine analysis.

Experimental

Organotrithiocarbonates were prepared as described earlier⁸. The purity of the compounds was checked by non-aqueous redox titration¹. The mercaptans (Fluka, Switzerland) were distilled twice before use. All other reagents used in this investigation were of guaranteed quality. Erma Photoelectric Colorimeter (Model A. E. 11), Japan was used for absorbance measurements.

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